

DEVELOPMENT OF THE DATABASE STRUCTURE OF AUTOMATIC LINES IN A DIGITAL SOFTWARE CONTROL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In this article, the procedure for developing the database structure of automatic lines was analyzed. The structure and composition of databases of automatic lines have been developed.*

Keywords: *sewing enterprises, technological process, automation in the production digital software control system, automated lines, new models, automation operators, data, databases, input data, output data.*

Introduction. In the modern information age, the quality and timing of model preparation for production are of particular importance. Therefore, one of the main tasks of the garment industry today is to increase product competitiveness, introduce modern database programs, IT technologies into technological processes, which provide the possibility of rapid replacement of the product assortment. One of the main directions for increasing the operability of light industry enterprises in a market economy and in conditions of free competition is the production of high-quality and competitive products for their development. To fulfill these conditions, it is necessary to constantly improve product manufacturing and accelerate the processes of designing new assortments.

To fulfill these conditions, it is necessary to constantly improve product manufacturing and accelerate the processes of designing new assortments. The introduction of digital technologies into the technological processes of garment enterprises is one of the most important issues. Successful process automation depends on effective information management, which, in turn, requires the creation of a reliable database. Properly designed database structure allows for access to necessary data, their regular updating, exchange of information related to new models and orders, and ensuring integrity [1, 2].

In databases, input and output data types are distinguished. Input data refers to data entered into a database: 1. Adding new records: When users or external programs enter new data into the database. 2. Data Update: Modifying the data available in the database (e.g., error correction or update). 3. Data import: Uploading data from external sources, such as CSV, Excel files, or other databases.

Output data is the collection of data related to the database by external systems, users, or other programs: 1. Questions (Query): Obtaining information from the database through the

SELECT query. 2. Reports and analyses: Creating reports or analyses using database data and sending the results to users or systems. 3. Data Export: Exporting data to files or external systems.

Input and output data are the basis of communication between the database data and other systems or users.

When forming a database, the following methods are used:

1. Requirements analysis: Identifying user needs and processes that need to be automated.
2. Data modeling: visualization of the database structure using methods such as UML (Unified Modeling Language).
3. Prototype development: Creating prototypes of the database and assessing its functionality.

Research methods. The structure of the database consists of:

1. Identifying key objects. In the first stage, it is necessary to identify the main objects stored in the database. Key objects for garment enterprises can be:

- Order: Customer order information, including order identifier, date, status, and customer information.

- Product: Characteristics of garments, such as assortment type, article number, name, category, price, and size.

- Material: Information about materials used in production, including identifier, type, article, price, and available inventory.

- Production process: Stages of the production process, IDs, process names, and duration.

- Employee: Employee information, ID, surname, position, and skills.

2. Determining the interrelationships of the data is also formed as a key stage [3,4,5]. After identifying the key objects, it is necessary to establish their interrelationships:

- Order - Product: Multiple models can be in one order, and the same type of model can be available in several orders. This "many to many" relationship requires creating an intermediate table called "Order_Product."

- Product - Material: One model can be made from several materials. This is a "more than one" connection, where in the "Product" table there is a field that links to the "Material" table.

- Production Process - Product: Each product must go through certain production processes. This is a "more than one" connection, where the necessary processes are indicated in the "Product" table.

- Employee - Production process: Each process can be performed by one or more employees. This "many to many" relationship requires creating an intermediate table called "Employee_Process."

3. Data modeling. The database model can be visualized using ER-diagrams (Entity-Relationship diagrams) (Fig. 1).

This allows for precise definition of objects, attributes, and their interrelationships. The structure can be as follows:

Order (ID, date, status, ID_client);

Product (ID, name, category, price, size);

Material (ID, name, price, backup);

Production process (ID, name, duration);

Employee (ID, surname, position, skills);

Order_Product (ID_order, ID_product, quantity);

Employee_process (ID_employee, ID_process);

Figure 1. DBMS structure and user interface.

For the effective functioning of the database, its integration with other information systems is important, for example:

Production Process Management Systems (PMS): These systems allow for the automation of production planning and control.

Inventory Management Systems (WMS): Integration with WMS ensures accurate accounting of materials and their movement across the warehouse.

CRM Systems: Linking the database to CRM improves order management and customer relationships.

The advantages of the database structure are:

- Facilitating data access: Users can quickly find the necessary information, which increases work efficiency.
- Ensuring data integrity: A correct database structure protects against duplicates and inconsistencies.
- Analysis and reporting: A tool for analyzing structural data and making management decisions.

Results. The formation of a database structure for the automation of technological processes of garment enterprises is an important stage that determines the success of automation. Proper database design and implementation allows for effective management of production processes, improving product quality, and optimizing costs [6, 7].

In the research work, the procedure for developing databases, the main requirements for the composition and structure of databases were studied in detail. Important stages of the process of developing the database structure of automated lines for garment enterprises have been identified. Because a comprehensively structured and correctly formulated database helps to effectively manage and optimize the production process of the enterprise. When creating a database, it is necessary to observe a certain procedure.

Automated lines of sewing machines with software management require an effective data storage system for process control, quality control, and performance analysis. Based on the

research results, a general structure of the database for automated lines in the digital program control system was formed (Fig. 2).

Figure 2

Conclusions. The structure of the proposed database consists of 7 main blocks. In the first block "Customers Customers," Customer ID - customer identifier, primary key; Name - customer name, Address - customer address, Contact - contact information are entered.

In the Second Orders block, Order ID is the primary key of the order identifier; Customer ID - customer identifier, external key; Model ID - external key of the model indicator; Quantity - quantity of items in the order; Data such as deadline - the deadline for fulfilling the order is entered.

Data of the third block Models - includes databases of models of garments. Model ID - model identifier, external key; Name - model name, article; Description - description of the model; Size - size of the product, Materials - information about the materials used is entered into the 3rd block.

Block 4 of the database Sewing Operation - technological processing of basic models; OperationID - operation identifier, primary key; Name - operation name; Description - description of operations; Time Required - time spent on performing the operation; MachineID - a machine identifier, containing information about external keys [8,9,10].

The 5th block of the database consists of Automated lines - information about automated lines in the programmed digital control system. Connections between automated lines; one order may include several production batches, one software automated machine may have multiple settings, one production batch may have multiple quality checks, one operator may be assigned to several software automated machines.

Block 6 contains basic information about programmable machines. That is - MachineID machine identifier, primary key; Name - machine name; Type - machine type; Capacity - machine productivity; Status - state of the machine; Overall dimensions of sewing machines with program control - information about the overall dimensions of program automatic machines is entered.

In the database, Block 7 Line Components - Additional Equipment in Automated Lines. Component ID - device identifier, primary key; Name - equipment name; Description - equipment description; Quantity - number of equipment in the line; LineID - line identifier, contains external key information.

The development of a database structure for automated lines of garment enterprises is a complex, but important process that allows for effective production management of information in the production processes of software systems databases.

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